

DIDACTIC PRINCIPLES OF USING INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN THE ORGANIZATION OF INDEPENDENT EDUCATION

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Abstract. *This article provides information on the pedagogical views of scientists of the Republic and abroad on independent education and independent studies of students and on the types of independent work in the auditorium, types of didactic materials used in independent work and on the independence of students.*

Keywords: *independent education, independent study, independence, independent education in the auditorium, expert, student, educational process, form of organization of independent education, position of organization of independent education.*

Currently, the higher education system is not only tasked with training personnel with deep knowledge in their specialty, but there are additional characteristics required from modern personnel in order for society to develop in all respects and achieve high goals. "mature personnel" and even "mature specialist" concepts change their essence a little, update them. The most important of these features is the ability of modern specialists to independently analyze received information through their advanced analytical thinking, sort and use the selected information for the development of science, the development of the country, and the well-being of the people. As the role of pedagogy is incomparable in this, in-depth study of pedagogy is important in the process of studying at higher educational institutions. The science of pedagogy has a great role in the rapid development of pedagogical knowledge and modern pedagogical technologies. Therefore, it is important to adapt the knowledge of students to the needs of the times and to ensure that they can achieve this knowledge through independent activities, and to form the ability to sort out the flow of information through their own logic in their activities at the next stage.

The student's level of independent thinking is reflected in many of his activities. For example, (considered from the point of view of all subjects) the use of a specific method in solving problems, writing creative essays, performing experimental work, making various items in the required situations, constructive approach in creating laboratory equipment, and all such processes require independent thinking of the student, and this clearly shows the degree to which the ability has been developed. Of course, it is not possible to give students all the modern knowledge of science in classes in the classroom. In the implementation of this, independent education should fulfill the task of complementing and developing important. Independent education serves to implement the formation of knowledge, skills and abilities defined in the curriculum of a particular subject and must be mastered by the student. p. 45].

Independent work, independent education and its theoretical foundations have been formed and developed throughout the history of mankind. However, M.Monten, Ya.A.Komensky, I.G.Pestalotsi and A.Disterweg are among the great historical didactics who have focused on its organizational and methodological support and the conditions for effective organization. will be appropriate. M.G. Garunov, B.N.Esipov, I.Ya.Lerner, P.I.Pidkasistiy, as well as A.A.

Abdukadirov, M.M.Aripov, U.Sh. Begimkulov, Q.T. Olimov and several other pedagogies from our country, who have conducted research in this field and are growing in recent years possible. Since the concepts of independent work, independent activity, and independent education are in some way's relative concepts, scientists have had a certain number of different, if necessary, completely different approaches to their content. For example, I. Ya. Lerner considered independent work as a teaching method, while P. I. Pidkasisti considered it as an educational tool and evaluated it as a form of educational and scientific knowledge. According to I.A. Danilov, "the activity determined by the teacher, but carried out for any knowledge obtained without his direct help, is an independent work" [2; p. 156] and so on. Scientists such as A.B.Usova, N.V.Kuzmina consider independent work as a teaching method, and V.Ya. Lyaudis, I.I.Ilyasov consider it a form of teaching. There are also evaluations as a type of educational activity, for example, according to the opinion of scientists such as N.G. Dairi, I.A. Danilov. The pedagogue and scientist B.P. Esipov, who spoke about the independent work and independent education of students, states that "the independent work of students included in the educational process is performed without the direct participation of the teacher, but based on his advice and instructions, it is done by the teacher at the specified time." [2; p. 158]. Since any form of education involves some amount of "independent learning," scholars agree on the positive skills that independent learning develops in the learner. Based on the above considerations, we give the author's definition of independent education as follows: Independent education is a systematic activity aimed at the learner's independent acquisition of knowledge, skills and abilities without the direct scientific support of the teacher, but based on his direct or indirect instructions in necessary cases. is a form of education that takes place mostly outside the classroom.

Independent work can be divided into the following types:

1. Independent performance of written assignments.
2. Graphic independent assignments.
3. Independent assignments of a practical nature.

Independent work and assignments are individual-didactic are classified according to their purpose as follows:

- tasks aimed at assimilation of information;
- tasks that teach how to process and apply knowledge;
- tasks that encourage the expression of knowledge, skills, skills based on their essence;
- tasks that develop analytical and, at the same time, critical thinking with a systematic study of ideas and thoughts [3; p. 164].

Preparation for independent education in a broad sense should begin with independent work in the classroom. The following can be used as didactic materials for independent work in the auditorium. The main and main requirement of the modern education system is to be able to independently solve the given problem, have the ability to think critically, and be able to express and defend their point of view based on their worldview. is to form a person who strives for the formation and perfection of his faith, constantly improves his knowledge, educates himself, strives for spiritual growth by correcting his shortcomings, applies his life skills in reality and searches for ways to achieve success in practice! After all, in the words of A.A. Abdukadirov, "The task of education today is to teach students to work independently in the conditions of the information-educational environment that is growing day by day, to use the flow of information wisely."

The types of didactic materials for independent works in the auditorium are as follows:

- Interesting and logical questions;
- Problem situations that require unconventional thinking;
- Crosswords on exact and natural sciences;
- Didactic materials;
- Problems (enhancing knowledge);
- Assignments encouraging a creative approach;
- Tasks intended for competitions;
- Project works carried out individually or in groups;
- Focuses on and supports students' creativity and individuality.

U.Sh. Begimkulov believes that the procedure for using electronic resources in the organization of independent education should be determined taking into account the individual characteristics of each student. [4, 27]. Currently, as experts in the field are conducting a number of researches and studies in order to study the important aspects of students' independent learning and to develop rules that naturally adapt to modern requirements, the existence of different approaches to this complex, comprehensive issue, different ways of developing independent education methodology (the main thing is to choose the most optimal one) and this is a natural situation. However, all scientists and researchers agree on the important role of independent education in the development of a person as a person. All leading pedagogues have recognized that independence is one of the leading virtues in a person, which means the ability to set specific goals and take an independent approach to their implementation.

According to the description in the encyclopedia of pedagogy, "Independence ensures a responsible attitude of a person to his actions, the ability to act consciously and actively not only in a familiar environment, but also in new conditions, requires non-standard decisions" [2; p. 224]. One of the scientific founders of pedagogy, the Russian scientist K. D. Ushinsky, substantiates the benefits of the independence of learners in the educational process with the positive aspects of their mental independence. He writes that children should work independently as much as possible, and the teacher should guide this independent work and provide students with materials. Many pedagogic scientists believe that if students complete tasks without the direct help of a teacher, the process will leave a deeper mark in the memory of students, and effective indicators will be achieved in education. "Students' independent work is a variety of individual and collective educational activities carried out on the basis of assignments in the classroom and outside the classroom or at home without the direct participation of teachers" [5; p. 17] is mentioned in one of the definitions.

In conclusion, independent education as a form of organizing the educational process can be approached from two different positions:

- as a developer of personal qualities (analytical and critical thinking, ability to sort information).
- it can be considered as a process that expands a person's scope of knowledge (theoretical and practical knowledge of the field). Every student becomes independent in life as he does independent work. We think that this will help students find their place in life.

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